

Minimum Upset/Failure Threshold Statistics of Devices for HERO/EMV Testing

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Abstract— Statistical models for minimum current thresholds of electro-explosive devices (EEDs) have historically employed Gaussian (or Normal) distribution functions when extrapolating to low-level firing probabilities. However, the Gaussian distribution is rather poor for making extrapolations to extrema and, at very low probabilities, often becomes negative which is clearly unphysical. The purpose of this paper is to further investigate the distribution function of EED thresholds through experimentally measuring the threshold of micro-fuses (acting as EED bridgewire surrogates). The Generalized Log-Logistic distribution was determined to have the best fit for the full set of empirical data. However, it was determined that the extreme values (i.e. minimum device thresholds) could be better modeled through application of the Generalized Pareto Theorem. Distribution parameters and associated confidence intervals are statistically determined through maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) methods.

I. INTRODUCTION

Device upset/failure threshold statistics are particularly of interest for Hazards of Electromagnetic Radiation to Ordnance (HERO) and Electromagnetic Vulnerability (EMV) testing. The assessment of HERO focuses primarily on the determination of probabilities of inadvertent actuation of electro-explosive devices (EEDs) when exposed to electromagnetic fields. Specifically, it is critical to be able to predict EED firings at low field stimulus levels.

Recent work has been done to experimentally characterize the coupling of electromagnetic energy to EED wires [1] and investigate the effects of different transient fields [2]. The Maximum Allowable Safe Stimulus (MASS) is the stimulus level at which an EED has a 10^{-6} probability to fire with ideal confidence [3]. The demonstration of such low probabilities from direct testing methods is not feasible based on the practical number of devices available for test and therefore inferential methods must be employed to make acceptable estimates. Low functioning probability points for EEDs have usually been estimated by extrapolating on the basis of an experimentally determined mean and standard deviation. This extrapolation process can lead to seriously faulty estimates unless great care is taken in fitting an appropriate probability distribution function to the experimental data.

The Brucceton method is the most widely used test method for obtaining and analysing firing data since it requires only modest sample sizes [3]. This test collects data near (within a

few standard deviations) the 50% probability of firing point. As such, it is not an ideal test for making the large extrapolations needed in the estimation of very low firing levels. There are many possible distribution functions which satisfactorily fit the data collected around the central stimulus range, but differ substantially at the low-end tails of their distribution functions. However, there are other EED sensitivity tests, such as Probit and Neyer methods, which provide statistical data better suited for making probability estimates at the lower end of the stimulus curve [4], [5].

Independent of the measurement method employed, a Gaussian (or Normal) distribution function has been used for data extrapolation extensively in the literature, manufacturing data, specifications, and standards. This Gaussian distribution, however, is rather poor for making the large extrapolations needed for low-level firing probabilities and is questionable even at moderately low probability values, such as 10^{-3} . At very low probabilities, the corresponding stimulus values (current, energy, etc.) often become negative, which is clearly unphysical. Alternatively, previous testing on 7890 wire-bridge MK 1 MOD 0 EEDs demonstrated that both Log-Normal and Log-Logistic probability distribution functions provide a reasonably good fit for the measured firing data and better mirror the firing distribution that results from the real physical processes responsible for EED activation [6]. This reference utilized the Bartlett method which provided more data in the lower region of the firing sensitivity distribution.

The purpose of this paper is to further investigate the distribution function of EED thresholds through experimentally measuring the threshold of over two hundred micro-fuses (acting as EED bridgewire surrogates) and then utilizing a distribution fitting tool to determine the best fit. The distribution is initially investigated around the empirical mean, but further investigation is done on the extreme low-end tail of the data which is of most interest for this application. Similar to the application of the Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) theorem for enclosure maximum fields [7], the Generalized Pareto Theorem is leveraged to fit the EED minimum thresholds.

The outline of the paper is as follows. In Section II, a discussion of the experimental design to measure the thresholds for over two hundred EED surrogates is discussed. Section III presents the best fit for the full set of empirical data (the Generalized Log-Logistic distribution) and application of the Generalized Pareto Theorem for fitting the extreme low-end tail of the distribution. Maximum Likelihood

Estimation (MLE) methods are utilized for distribution function parameter estimation and confidence intervals.

II. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN & APPROACH

Due to the high cost of EEDs, threshold measurements for this work were measured on EED surrogates, specifically very-fast-acting micro-fuse devices, which have historical precedence for use as surrogates within the HERO test community. Direct inject measurements were performed utilizing the susceptibility test circuit depicted in Figure 1. The EED surrogate thresholds were measured using an automated test sequence protocol to help ensure each device was exposed to the same stimulus levels. The protocol consisted of starting at a predefined low amplitude, applying the voltage for three seconds, then removing the stimulus for ten seconds, followed by increasing the amplitude by a predefined increment. This was repeated until the micro-fuse failed and the current through the fuse which caused failure was recorded as the threshold. Output voltage (V_{out}) measurements across the 5 ohm resistor in series to the micro-fuse provided direct calculation of current thresholds. A photograph of the test setup is provided in Figure 2, which includes a programmable voltage source (V_{in}), bread board circuit, DC power supply, voltage monitoring device and control computer/software.

Fig. 1. Direct-inject susceptibility test circuit.

Fig. 2. Photograph of direct-inject susceptibility test setup and very-fast-acting micro-fuse (inset).

Fig. 3. Micro-fuse threshold voltages

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS & DISTRIBUTION FITTING

A. Generalized Log-Logistic Distribution

The two hundred and sixteen individual micro-fuse threshold voltage measurements are provided in Figure 3 and as depicted, threshold voltages range from roughly .37 to .42 volts. A distribution fitting tool was then utilized to determine the best fit for the full data set utilizing both Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Anderson-Darling tests and it was determined that the Generalized Log-Logistic distribution provided an optimal fit. This indicated that the micro-fuses acted as good EED surrogates since previous MK 1 MOD 0 EED thresholds were demonstrated to fit the Log-Logistic distribution function adequately [6]. The Generalized Log-Logistic cumulative distribution function (cdf) is defined as:

$$F(x) = \frac{1}{1 + \left(1 + \frac{\varepsilon(x-\mu)}{\sigma}\right)^{-1/\varepsilon}} \quad (1)$$

where μ , σ , and ε represent the location, scale and shape parameters, x represents the threshold voltages, and F is defined on x : $1 + \frac{\varepsilon(x-\mu)}{\sigma} > 0$.

Maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) techniques were then employed for determining the best estimates for the fitting parameters and for standard deviation and confidence interval calculations. This method assigns different probability densities to the observed data for specific values of the parameters μ , σ , and ε . The probability of the observed data as a function of the parameters is then termed the likelihood function. Typically, the log-likelihood function is utilized due to the convenience of summing values and since the logarithm function is monotonic, maximums will occur at the same point. The log-likelihood function for the Log-Logistic distribution is given by:

$$\ell(\mu, \sigma, \varepsilon) = -\ln(\sigma) - \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varepsilon}\right) \sum_{i=1}^N \ln \left[1 + \frac{\varepsilon(x_i - \mu)}{\sigma}\right] - 2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \ln \left[1 + \left(1 + \frac{\varepsilon(x_i - \mu)}{\sigma}\right)^{-1/\varepsilon}\right] \quad (2)$$

Fig. 4. Generalized Log-logistic cumulative distribution function with threshold voltage measurements

requiring $1 + \frac{\varepsilon(x-\mu)}{\sigma} > 0$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$ where N is the number of threshold data points. Therefore, the estimated parameters ($\hat{\mu}$, $\hat{\sigma}$ and $\hat{\varepsilon}$) are the values which maximize the log-likelihood function within its respective bounds. Figure 4 provides the Generalized Log-Logistic cdf plot utilizing the MLE parameters and demonstrates very good agreement between the empirical and fitted distribution function.

Additionally for large enough N , a multidimensional MLE parameter (in this case consisting of $\hat{\mu}$, $\hat{\sigma}$ and $\hat{\varepsilon}$) asymptotically approaches a multivariate normal distribution (MVN) and therefore, a 3x3 variance-covariance matrix can be derived from the observed information matrix. Then by theorem [8, pg. 33], the maximum likelihood estimate of any function of MLE parameter estimates can be obtained by simple substitution of the estimation parameters into the respective function. Therefore, by inverting (1) and defining $F(x) \equiv p$ and $z_p = \frac{1}{p} - 1$, we can calculate the maximum likelihood estimate of $\hat{x}$ as:

$$\hat{x}_p = \hat{\mu} - \frac{\hat{\sigma}}{\hat{\varepsilon}} [1 - z_p^{-\hat{\varepsilon}}] \quad \text{for } \hat{\varepsilon} \neq 0 \quad (3)$$

and by the delta method, the maximum likelihood estimator of any scalar function of MLE parameter estimates (specifically $\hat{x}_p$) is normally distributed with variance V_{x_p} :

$$V_{x_p} \approx \nabla x_p^T \cdot V \cdot \nabla x_p \quad (4)$$

where V is the variance-covariance matrix and ∇x_p is the vector gradient of x_p evaluated at ($\hat{\mu}$, $\hat{\sigma}$ and $\hat{\varepsilon}$). Therefore, the maximum likelihood estimate for the sample threshold $\hat{x}_p$ and its associated 95% confidence intervals can be determined from (3) and (4) respectively.

The MLE of the thresholds ($\hat{x}_p$) and its associated confidence intervals are generally plotted on a quantile estimation plot (commonly referred to as the return level plot in extreme value theory). This plot compares the predicted

Fig. 5. Generalized Log-logistic quantile estimation plot with threshold voltage measurements and 95% confidence intervals

Table 1. Generalized Log-logistic parameter estimates & var-cov matrix

	$\hat{\mu}$	$\hat{\sigma}$	$\hat{\varepsilon}$
Parameters	.39	.005	-.04
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Var-Cov Matrix	$\hat{\mu}$	$\hat{\sigma}$	$\hat{\varepsilon}$
$\hat{\mu}$	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$-1.4 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$-7.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$\hat{\sigma}$	$-1.4 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$9.7 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$-1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$\hat{\varepsilon}$	$-7.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$-1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$

values $\hat{x}_p$ from (3), which are based on the parameter estimates, with the empirical data x_p , both plotted against z_p on a logarithmic scale (over $0 < p < 1$). One advantage to this type of plot is that the data is rescaled to provide more information into the goodness of fit for the model at the tails of the distribution. In this case, the low-end region (i.e. minimum thresholds) is of most interest. As shown in Figure 5, the predicted thresholds have a very good fit to the empirical data around the mean. However, the low end tail of the model ($z_p \sim 100$) seems to be trending downward, while the data seems to indicate a leveling off.

It is important to note that the direction of the tail of the distribution (i.e. convex vs. concave) is determined by the sign of the shape parameter ($\hat{\varepsilon}$). As indicated in Table 1, the shape parameter is very close to zero. The 95% confidence intervals of the $\hat{\varepsilon}$ can be determined from its variance term within the variance-covariance matrix to be $[-0.13, 0.05]$ which does extend slightly above zero. This is consistent with what is observed in the quantile estimate plot and it appears that the data around the mean has a stronger influence on the sign of the shape parameter than the extreme low-end tail of the distribution.

B. Generalized Pareto Distribution

Due to the limitations with adequately modeling the extreme low-end tail of the device thresholds utilizing the Generalized Log-Logistic distribution and its associated

Fig. 6. Generalized Pareto cumulative distribution function

consequences for extrapolations to low-level firing probabilities, a more effective model is necessary. Previous work has been done for modeling extreme values (specifically maximum fields within RF reflective enclosures) utilizing the Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) distribution [7]. The GEV distribution utilizes data blocking and modeling the ensuing blocked data's maximums (or minimums). In the case of enclosure maximum fields, measuring the large number of required samples for use in data blocking was entirely manageable. However, when measuring device thresholds, it is significantly more difficult to get large sample sizes and modeling blocked maxima (or minima) can be very wasteful and inefficient.

However, similar to how the GEV theorem states that the distribution function of blocked maximums asymptotically approaches one of the three families of extreme value distributions, the Generalized Pareto Theorem indicates that threshold excesses have a corresponding approximate distribution within the Generalized Pareto family of distributions [8]. The two approaches are very similar and directly related, contrasting primarily in the way extreme values are defined (i.e. blocked extremes vs. threshold exceedances). Since we are primarily concerned with minimums, by selecting a low threshold u and defining $y = u - x$, the distribution function of y , conditional on $x < u$, is:

$$H(y) = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{ky}{s}\right)^{-1/k} \quad (5)$$

where s and k are the distribution fitting parameters, and H is defined on y : $1 + \frac{ky}{s} > 0$. The log-likelihood function for the Generalized Pareto distribution is then given by:

$$\ell(s, k) = -M \cdot \ln(\sigma) - \left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right) \sum_{i=1}^M \ln \left[1 + \frac{ky}{s}\right] \quad (6)$$

requiring $1 + \frac{ky}{s} > 0$ for $i = 1, \dots, M$ where M is the number of data points below the threshold u .

Fig. 7. Generalized Pareto quantile estimation plot and 95% confidence intervals

Table 2. Generalized Pareto parameter estimates & var-cov matrix

	$\hat{s}$	$\hat{k}$
Parameters	.011	-.47
Var-Cov Matrix		
$\hat{s}$	$3.9 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$-2.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$\hat{k}$	$-2.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-2}$

As was the case for determining block sizes for the GEV, threshold selection is very critical. Too high of a threshold will introduce bias due to violating the asymptotic basis of the Generalized Pareto model, and too low a threshold will severely limit the number of data points available for model estimation. There are multiple methods to aid in threshold selection, one of which was employed for this effort. MLE techniques were utilized iteratively over a range of threshold selections and the stability of parameter estimates was investigated. It is typically practiced to select the lowest threshold as possible, while still maintaining both a reasonable approximation and stability in parameter estimates. A threshold of .391V was determined to be optimal for this set of empirical data. The Generalized Pareto cdf plot is depicted in Figure 6 and demonstrates good agreement between the empirical and fitted distribution function.

It is again advantageous to work with quantiles and so by inverting (5) and defining $H(y) \equiv p$ and $m_p = \frac{1}{1-p}$, the maximum likelihood estimate of $\hat{y}$ is calculated as:

$$\hat{y}_p = \frac{\hat{s}}{\hat{k}} [m_p^{\hat{k}} - 1] \quad \text{for } \hat{k} \neq 0 \quad (7)$$

The MLE parameters and variance-covariance matrix are provided in Table 2 and the variance of $\hat{y}_p$ can then be determined by again applying the delta method as:

$$V_{y_p} \approx \nabla y_p^T \cdot V \cdot \nabla y_p \quad (8)$$

where V is the variance-covariance matrix and ∇y_p is the

vector gradient of y_p evaluated at $(\hat{\beta}$ and $\hat{\kappa})$. The Generalized Pareto quantile estimation plot with 95% confidence intervals is provided in Figure 7. As depicted, there is a very good fit between the estimated and empirical data with the model correctly trending with the measured extreme values ($m_p \sim 10$ to 100). This indicates a significant improvement and allows for the large extrapolations needed for determining low-level firing probabilities.

IV. CONCLUSION

Experimental voltage threshold measurements were performed on EED surrogates utilizing a direct inject susceptibility test circuit and an automated test sequence protocol. A distribution fitting tool was then utilized to assess the best fit for the full data set and it was determined that the Generalized Log-Logistic distribution provided an optimal fit. This indicates that the micro-fuses acted as good EED surrogates since previous EEDs have been demonstrated to fit the Log-Logistic distribution. Investigation into the Generalized Log-Logistic distribution fit indicated that the predicted thresholds aligned very well with the empirical data around the mean. However, the distribution's fit at the extreme low-end tail trended away from the empirical extreme values. This introduces significant errors when making the large extrapolations needed for predicting low-level HERO firing probabilities.

In order to better model the extreme low-end tail of the empirical data, the Generalized Pareto theorem was leveraged. Values below a set threshold were modeled and parameter estimates and confidence intervals were calculated utilizing MLE methods. It was determined that the Generalized Pareto distribution was a good representation of the data extremes (i.e. minimum device thresholds) and can be better leveraged for extrapolations to low-level firing probabilities.

The device threshold distribution discussed in this paper and the maximum received power distribution within RF reflective enclosures [7] are being utilized as part of a method for statistically assessing the magnitude of a system/sub-system's hardness or safety margin to upset/failure. This method, specifically termed the Electromagnetic Probability-of-effect Assessment Tool (EMPAT) utilizes the hardness margin (from structural reliability analysis) to statistically determine the probability of effect, and its associated confidence intervals, for EED devices (or sensitive electronics) when exposed to maximum fields within RF reflective enclosures.

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REFERENCES

[1] J.J. Pantoja, N. Pena, N. Mora, F. Rachidi, F. Vega, and R. Roman, "On the Electromagnetic Susceptibility of Hot Wire-Based Electroexplosive Devices to RF Sources," *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, Vol 55, No. 4, pp. 754-763, August 2013.

[2] J.J. Pantoja, N. Pena, N. Mora, F. Rachidi, F. Vega, and R. Roman, "Characterization, Modeling, and Statistical Analysis of the Electromagnetic Response of Inert Improvised Explosive Devices," *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, Vol. 56, No. 2, pp. 393-403, April 2014.

[3] Electro-Explosive Devices Assessment And Test Methods For Characterization - Guidelines For STANAG 4560, NATO Allied Ordnance Publication AOP-43, 3rd ed., June 2010.

[4] B.T. Neyer and J. Gageby, "ISO 14304 Annex B: All-Fire/No-Fire Test and Analysis Methods," *Proceedings of the Seventeenth Symposium on Explosives and Pyrotechnics*, Essington, PA, April 1999.

[5] M. Paradis and K. Pfaab, "Overview Of The Reliability Methods For Explosive Devices by the GTPS," *7th ESA/CNES International Workshop On Space Pyrotechnics*, ESTEC, September 2008.

[6] D.W. Gaylor and J.A. Merrill, "Distribution of the Firing Energy for the Squib MK 1 MOD 0," U.S. Naval Weapons Laboratory Dahlgren, Research Report SU-238/1, Sept. 1966.

[7] C. Hager IV and G. Tait, "Maximum Received Power Statistics within RF Reflective Enclosures for HERO/EMV Testing" in *Proc. IEEE Symposium Electromagnetic Compatibility*, Santa Clara, CA, pp. 237-241, March 2015.

[8] S. Coles, *An Introduction to Statistical Modeling of Extreme Values*. Great Britain: Springer-Verlag London Limited, 2001.

[9] E.E. Lewis, *Introduction to Reliability Engineering*, 2nd ed. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 1996.

[10] P. Meyer, *Introductory Probability and Statistical Applications*. 2nd ed. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley Publishing Company Co. Inc., 1970.